

SOME METHODOLOGICAL APPROACHES TO TEACHING A FOREIGN LANGUAGE

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Abstract: *The article considers the history, the founders, differences, peculiarities, principles, main characteristics, advantages and disadvantages of different approaches to teaching foreign languages.*

Key words: *method, approach, communication, integration, language skills, acquisition, principle, aspect of language*

Annotatsiya: *Maqolada chet tillarini o'qitishga turli yondashuvlarning tarixi, asoschilari, farqlari, xususiyatlari, tamoyillari, asosiy xususiyatlari, afzalliklari va kamchiliklari ko'rib chiqiladi.*

Tayanch soʻzlar: *usul, yondashuv, muloqot, integratsiya, til malakasi, oʻzlashtirish, tamoyil, til jihati*

Аннотация: *В статье рассматриваются история, основатели, различия, особенности, принципы, основные характеристики, преимущества и недостатки различных подходов к преподаванию иностранных языков.*

Ключевые слова: *метод, подход, коммуникация, интеграция, языковые навыки, приобретение, принцип, аспект языка*

The history of foreign language teaching methodology, the emergence and development of new teaching methods, has always been closely linked to new trends in linguistics, psychology, and pedagogy. The data of these sciences are capable of fundamentally changing the approach to teaching, developing new methods, leading to the emergence of new systems and models of teaching. Currently, Uzbekistan is undergoing a transformation in the methods of teaching English. Previously, priority

in teaching a foreign language was given to grammar, vocabulary, reading, and literary translation. Language acquisition was carried out through a long, routine process. Tasks were offered quite uniformly: reading the text, translating, memorizing new words, retelling, exercises based on the text. It is not surprising that the language knew units well.

The problems faced by methodologists in Uzbekistan and abroad turned out to be largely similar. The most important problem of learning became the connection between the content and formal aspects of language. If the structural organization of language is promoted to the first place, and lexicon is assigned an auxiliary role, then in the learning process, mastering the substantive side of speech slows down. However, a predominantly meaningful, lexical approach often leads to gross grammatical and communicatively significant errors, which also hinders effective communication in a foreign language. The solution to this problem lies in connecting both the content and formal aspects of language in the learning process. Different views on the interests of the individual, their needs and capabilities, as well as didactic techniques, contributed to the emergence of different approaches to teaching foreign languages. Below we will look through some of them.

In the history of foreign language teaching methodology, there are various approaches and methods to teaching foreign languages. The term "teaching approach" (Eng. approach - approach, approach) was introduced into scientific discourse by English methodologist A. Anthony to denote the initial provisions used by researchers regarding the nature of language and methods of mastering it. As a component of the language teaching system, the approach serves as the most general methodological basis for teaching, characterizing existing viewpoints on the subject of teaching and the possibilities of mastering it in the learning process. According to methodologists, the approach to teaching represents a point of view on the essence of the subject that needs to be taught, is used as the most general methodological basis for research in a specific field of knowledge, and defines the researcher's

activity aimed at studying a particular phenomenon. To substantiate the rationality of using an integrated approach, it is necessary to analyze various methodological approaches to teaching a foreign language [1,92].

Humanistic approach. This approach is associated with the name of K. Roger. According to this approach, learning should be personality-oriented, contribute to the development and realization of the individual's sense of self-awareness. The humanistic approach means the need to cultivate in students a sense of responsibility, self-esteem, and self-control. This approach assumes a humane and free nature of learning and rejects the development of curricula and plans, i.e., it is practically uncontrolled [2,177].

Global approach. According to this approach, language learning should be based on the material of inseparable blocks that are practiced as a whole, from top to bottom; from the general perception of the material to subsequent identification and awareness of its parts. In this case, preference is given to group and pair work, communication [3,338].

Behaviorist approach. The founder of this approach is considered to be B. Skinner. According to this approach, the learning process is primarily influenced by the world surrounding the individual. Behaviorism describes learning as an operationally conditioned process (different variants of human behavior), when an individual responds to a stimulus with a certain behavior. In this case, the teacher's positive reaction encourages students to independently perform a certain set of actions, while the negative reaction contributes to their refusal [4,285].

Cognitive approach. The authors of this approach are considered to be J. Bruner and W. Rivers. This approach relies on the principle of consciousness in learning and the theory of socioconstructivism, according to which students are active participants in the learning process, and not the object of the teacher's teaching activity. Depending on the individual psychological characteristics and qualities of

the individual, students have their own path of cognition, their own cognitive style, which influences the choice of learning strategies [5,243].

The structural approach focuses on the grammatical aspect of language. It is based on the provisions of structural linguistics and the behaviorist direction in psychology. According to this approach, learning involves mastering a number of grammatical structures that are introduced as speech patterns. The automation of speech patterns is carried out under the guidance of the teacher in exercises on setting, imitating, filling in gaps, etc [6,91].

Instrumental approach. This approach considers the studied linguistic and speech phenomena as statistical units, frozen patterns, which should be generated and understood in the learning process. Within the framework of this approach, a certain period of learning ends for the student with the creation of some speech product - monologue, dialogue, writing, etc [7,183].

The deductive approach involves explaining the rule and training it in practice, i.e., the path from the general to the particular, from the form to its implementation. The deductive approach underlies the grammatical-translation method, where students first learn a rule and then perform exercises. The deductive approach is time-efficient and contributes to understanding the structure and form of linguistic phenomena. However, memorizing rules can become a single goal, which makes it difficult to develop communication skills.

The inductive approach implies a path from the particular to the general, from the use of a lexical or grammatical phenomenon to understanding its form. The inductive approach underlies the audio-linguistic method, where students work according to the model, use a linguistic unit through imitation, mechanical repetition, but do not formulate a rule verbally. Skill formation occurs through mechanical repetition and memorization. Students become familiar with the grammatical phenomenon and its use in speech, which facilitates communication but hinders self-control [8,88].

Lexical approach. Within this approach, vocabulary is studied in all its diversity. Special attention is paid to the formation of word usage skills. According to this approach, the leading one in the learning process is listening, i.e., a receptive type of activity. The formation of receptive skills should be ahead of the formation of productive oral speech skills. Speech training begins after the skills of listening to the text have been formed. Training is based on transferring listening skills to other types of speech activity. In this case, the main focus is on the meaning of the studied linguistic phenomenon, not its form [9,264].

Integrated approach. According to this approach, language learning occurs through real communication, which contributes to the development of students' communicative competence. Students quickly learn the richness and complexity of a foreign language in the process of communication, language becomes a means of interaction and information exchange, and this approach allows the teacher to practice and develop all language skills (reading, listening, writing, and speaking) of students simultaneously and inseparably. The integration of language skills also allows for the study of real content, not just language forms. [10,228]

Communicative approach. This approach encourages students to show their own activity, joy, and pleasure in communicating with each other. Based on this approach, students develop an understanding that mastering a language means being able to use it as a means of social communication in real communication situations. The purpose of this approach is for students to be able to use various strategies for indirect and direct communication. At the same time, the conceptual system of learning is developed and a linguistic picture of the world is formed, which is possessed by the native speaker of the language being studied [11,243].

In conclusion, different, sometimes diametrically opposite, approaches to describing the mechanisms of foreign language acquisition in educational settings can be generalized in "global hypotheses," i.e., in scientific assumptions regarding how to generally describe the process of foreign language acquisition. Analysis of

these hypotheses shows that the main differences between them are related to the problem of the relationship between native and foreign languages, a person's innate abilities for language, and the language and speech experience acquired in the language being studied, with the definition of psycholinguistic mechanisms that ensure the functioning of the language acquisition process.

References:

1. Бим И.Л. Подход к проблеме упражнений с позиций иерархии целей и задач // Общая методика обучения иностранным языкам: Хрестоматия. - М.: Русский язык, 1991.
2. Stevick E.W. Humanism in Language Teaching. - Oxford: CUP, 1991.
3. Field J. Key concepts in ELT: 'bottom-up and 'top-down // ELT Journal, 1999
4. Williams M.L., Burden R.L. Psychology for Language Teachers: A Social Constructivist Approach. - Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 1997.
5. Rivers W.M., Communicating Naturally in a Second Language: Theory and Practice in Language Teaching, - Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 1989.
6. Ellis R. The Structural Syllabus and Second Language Acquisition // TESOL Quarterly, 1993.
7. Hutchinson T., Waters A. English for Specific Purposes: A Learner-centered Approach, - Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 1996.
8. Gollin J. Key Concepts in ELT. Deductive vs. Inductive Language Learning // ELT Journal, 1998.
9. Lewis M. The Lexical Approach. London; Language Teaching Publications, 1993.
10. Scarcella R.C., Oxford R.L. The Tapestry of Language Learning. - Heinle & Heinle Publishers Boston, Massachusetts USA, 1992.
11. Brumfit Ch. & Johnson K. The Communicative Approach to Language Teaching. -Oxford: Oxford University Press, 1979.